
D5.5 Towards people-centred EPCs: Guidelines and recommendations for development of people centred EPC products and services

Task 5.5 Guidelines for development of people-centred
EPC products and services

WP5 Towards people-centred EPCs

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Executive summary

This report is an outcome of crossCert project Task 5.5. Firstly and most importantly, the report presents the crossCert perspective on what people-centred EPC products and services actually means. Instead of highlighting aspects of technical and political expertise, often framed in terms of EPC methods or policy, the report highlights the people around the EPCs. The conceptual purpose of the deliverable is, therefore, to present EPCs as social objects – not only acknowledging that they exist *within* our society but also trying to show how they exist as such, how they influence (and are influenced by) the socio-cultural dynamics in which they exist, and how they could be made more impactful with regard to the purpose(s) associated with the concept. The practical purpose, reflecting the objectives of Task 5.5 as well as other WP5 tasks, is to suggest guidelines and recommendations for development of people-centred EPC Products and Services.

In practical terms, the report is largely a review of work within crossCert Work Package 5, referencing recommendations and best practices noted in the following deliverables:

- **D5.1 Report on existing EPC attitudes, expectations and needs (Bancič and Vetršek 2022)** – Offers a critical people-centred interdisciplinary perspective on understanding EPCs.
- **D5.2 Survey and workshop results of EPC end-users (Jenkins et al. 2024)** – Summarises the results of an end-user survey across European countries and a subsequent workshop investigating user needs for EPCs.
- **D5.3 Report on training and education services for certified EPC issuers (Simeonov 2024)** – Provides an overview of the training schemes for EPC issuers in the ten crossCert countries.
- **D5.4 Report on promotion and marketing of EPC products and services (Turfin 2024)** – Offers a pioneering analysis of current EPC promotion and marketing, as well as a framework for development of effective future EPC campaigns.

The main independent result of Task 5.5 are **four crossCert infographics**, developed independently from other WP5 tasks but with the aim to complement their work and results:

- **EPC Journey**, mapping the process of creation of the EPCs.
- **EPC Design**, guides the reader's thought through stages of Design thinking, tailored to the specific case of designing EPC Products and Services.
- **EPC Assessor's Journey**, mapping the career path of certified EPC Assessors.
- **EPC Promotion and Marketing**, mapping the crossCert approach to promotion and marketing of all things EPC.

The infographics are essentially graphical representations of different segments of the EPC System, specifically those with a potential for enhanced people-centred design. Developed with help of a professional designer, the infographics function as a tool for a structured analysis and assessment of the state of existing EPC Systems. Readers of all knowledge backgrounds will find them useful for a better understanding of the EPC System and of the different profiles involved in the system. EPC professionals will find them useful as a tool to segment the EPC system into logical building blocks and systematically seek for improvements of the existing systems. Finally, the infographics can also be used as promotional materials by those that raise public awareness about the importance of EPCs, didactic materials by those who teach EPC-related topics, or workshop materials by those who plan workshops on EPC related topics.

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Glossary of key terms

Table 1. Glossary of terms used in crossCert Deliverable 5.5.

EPC System	<p>A functional network of stakeholders and institutions that enable, co-create and otherwise support the existence and functioning of the national EPC Schemes. Besides people who drive the system, it also includes the EPC Scheme (see below) and other non-animate means used by representatives of the EPC Service Support Network (see below) in their efforts to keep the system working.</p>
EPC Scheme	<p>A conceptual and legislative framework that includes protocols and methods that define the national rules and standards regarding the issuing of EPCs. In contrast to the EPC System, which concepts all EPC related things in terms of practice, the EPC Scheme is a category that refers to the bureaucratic base necessary for existence and functioning of the EPC System. In simple terms, the EPC Scheme only exists on paper while the EPC System is everything that happens in real life because we have the EPC Scheme in the first place.</p>
EPC Service Support Network	<p>Refers to profiles that develop the conceptual framework for implementation of the national EPC Schemes, as well as stakeholders that enable and/or implement (enforce or exercise) the official conceptual framework.</p>
EPC Assessors	<p>Refers to people trained and certified to do EPC assessments. In essence, they are part of the EPC Service Support Network yet play a pivotal role in translating EPC theory into practice, connecting the EPC System with the public. The term EPC issuer(s) is often interchangeably used to refer to the same EPC profile. Here we use EPC Assessor only because we find it more appropriate to stress the role of individual experts who work with clients on the field (during site visits) to produce EPCs as opposed to larger organisations that function as a sort of an 'EPC issuing authority', which are sometimes associated with the more general term 'issuer'.</p>
EPC Expert Users	<p>Refers to people assumed to possess considerable knowledge in the area of buildings and the built environment, which also implies a capacity to interpret EPCs as advanced users, and possibly use EPCs as part of their professional practice (planning of building renovations or retrofits, real estate transactions, granting loans or credits based on EPCs, etc.).</p>
EPC General Users	<p>Refers to people assumed to possess a lesser extent of relevant EPC-related knowledge yet expected to interpret and use EPCs meaningfully in pursuit of their specific goals related to buildings (buying, renting or selling of buildings, renovating buildings, etc.).</p>
EPC Products and Services	<p>As established in crossCert D5.1, EPC Products and Services is a notion that refers to (1) the EPC assessment and certification service and (2) the EPC as the main product delivered to the customer (see Bančič and Vetršek 2022: 54). In addition to these basic two elements, we can consider any service or product that supports or increases value of the basic two elements as an auxiliary EPC product or service.</p>

1 Introduction

This report is focused on aspects that highlight the role of people in the context of energy performance assessments of buildings, specifically those practiced in the context of national policies and regulations based on the EU's Energy Performance of Buildings Directive¹ (EPBD). It does not focus on the Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) or its associated technical aspects, such as specifics of the methods used to gather data and to calculate the EPC, nor does it address the measurable (objective) accuracy of the EPCs, which are the product of the assessment process. These aspects are problematised and discussed extensively in several other crossCert deliverables (Fueyo et al. 2022; Sayfikar and Jenkins 2022; Sayfikar and Jenkins 2023; Sayfikar and Jenkins 2024), as well as in other already existing resources (see Taxeri 2023: 14-16). In relation to the technical details of EPC assessment, the aspects highlighted in this report can be described as contextual. We focus on the EPC assessment service(s), which can be characterised as processes that happen before and after the calculation and issuing of EPCs. We think about EPCs as products, highlighting some design and practical aspect of its production process. Finally, we also highlight the aspects of promotion and marketing of all EPC-related things, stressing the importance of strategic communication efforts in processes of policy making and implementation.

1.1 EPCs are good enough

To think effectively about the outlined contextual aspects, the working assumption of this report is that **EPCs as we know them today**, which includes the methods used for their production, **are already of sufficient quality to serve the various purposes they are associated with**, namely:

- To provide an assessment (technical evaluation) of the energy performance of a building and propose potential measures to improve the performance.
- To influence the real-estate market by serving as an objective reference point for valuation of quality of housing, and thus as one of the indicators of property's value.
- To direct the construction market developments and support the sector of building renovations and retrofitting.
- To provide ground for systemic data-based analysis and evaluation of the quality of housing stock, as well as monitoring and evaluation of improvements through time.

(see Bančič and Vetršek 2022: 26-28)

The above premise is not simultaneously an assertion that the methods currently used for producing EPCs are perfect, that they are not to be continuously tested, or that they could not or do not need to be improved. On the contrary, the objective quality of the EPCs is indeed a key condition to ensure their useful value. In other words, measurable quality of EPCs should be considered the basic condition for any contemporary EPC System to function effectively and reliably. By assuming that the quality of EPCs is good enough we simply put this question aside, on the second place, and highlight other important aspects of how to improve the EPC systems which are often left un(der)discussed.

¹ Available online: https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/energy-performance-buildings-directive_en#documents [Last accessed: 27. 06. 2024]

1.2 The issue with debating quality of EPCs

“The battle regarding EPC theory and methods can only be fought and (hopefully) won in the relevant spheres of expertise and policymaking, and not in the interaction between the EPC assessors and EPC users, where a quality product and service is (or should be) simply delivered, rather than negotiated.”
(Bančić and Vetršek 2022: 12)

Quality, as a concept, is an inherently relative measure that depends on specific contexts. The variety of expert standards and traditions across different EU countries, not to mention the different political, economic and socio-cultural contexts, render comparability of EPCs a very difficult task, to say the least. This is often presented as a problem, particularly in the light of aspirations to unify national/regional systems with the purpose to enhance comparability of EPCs across Europe. This tendency, often referred to as ‘harmonisation’ of the European EPC schemes (or elements of it), can be beneficial, as argued by Arcipowska et al. (2014), Serna-González et al. (2021), Carnero Melero (2023) and the likes. However, it is also necessary to recognise the limits of such aspirations. After all, the expert debates about the ‘correct’ way to assess the energy efficiency of buildings seem to be endless, witnessed by the simple fact that more than two decades after the first broad introduction of EPCs at the EU level this issue is still being discussed.

Perhaps the biggest issue with expert debates fixated on the quality of EPCs is that they are often instrumentalised as an excuse for not even *trying* to use EPCs in real life scenarios. Accusations and complaints often seem to be used as a cover for resisting change, or otherwise, efforts to maintain the status quo. Typical complaints over the assessment and calculation method(s) used for issuing EPCs tend to shift the responsibility to the developers of the calculation method or some other part (or representative) of the EPC System. Similarly, complaints over superficiality or inaccuracy in the production process tend to shift the responsibility to the EPC Assessors, who are often accused of performing their work poorly. Such complaints are voiced by building managers or owners who dislike how the EPC System influences the ways buildings are thought about and cared for. Such opinions are also shared by real-estate agents who dislike the change EPCs induce in the real estate market, or construction workers and other professionals from the construction sector who dislike the ongoing change in ways how buildings are built and renovated. Finally, property owners, managers, and building users use such arguments to fend off their increased responsibilities regarding the reduction of energy use in buildings.

People in general do not like change, especially if it requires work, an investment of time, or if it carries some form of negative financial consequences (costs), even if only on the short run. All the above listed cases imply at least one of these elements. Furthermore, change generally requires time and effort and is often perceived (in the mind) or lived (in practice) as messy, complicated, and expensive. These associations, for example, are exactly what comes to people’s minds when they think about building renovations (see Nieboer and Straub 2018; Cernišek et al. 2019; Ebrahimigharehbaghi et al. 2019), and this –in terms of the non-expert crowd, which in fact is the vast majority– is arguably the main thing EPCs were designed to have us thinking about. People also do not like changes that require us to alter our established work processes, to reconsider existing beliefs, or, as already mentioned, to face potentially negative effects on our earnings. To illustrate, when discussing the ‘impact on the real estate market’ or the necessity to change established practices in customer or citizen interaction, many professionals in the built environment and real estate sectors—the EPC Expert Users, such as architects, designers, contractors, and real estate agents—often perceive this as ‘unnecessary effort’ or a potential decrease in hourly rates, as indicated by research done in U-CERT project (see Bančić et al. 2020; Bančić et al. 2021).

1.3 EPBD as a philosophy

In the light of issues outlined above, this report aims to suggest ways to break out of this debate. Firstly, we suggest thinking about the EPBD as a kind of ‘philosophy’ of evaluating the energy efficiency of

buildings. In this way, the national approaches to how this is done in practice do not need to be labelled 'wrong' or 'right'. If anything, they should perhaps be labelled 'better' or 'worse', and even that should not be measured by quality (accuracy) of individual EPCs, but best by considering the impact of an EPC System with regard to the above-listed purposes (energy saved, motivating renovation of buildings, influencing the property markets, etc.).

Secondly, and perhaps more importantly, we suggest putting the debates about the quality of EPCs aside altogether, no matter how important they might seem to be, and to focus on other aspects that can render the already existing EPC Systems (more or less) people-centred and ultimately more impactful. Rather than focusing on the prescribed calculation methods and tools, policy diction enshrined in laws and regulation, or even the results and recommendations presented in the EPC as a final product, we suggest to approach the EPC Systems as dynamic processes. We suggest thinking about how national EPC Systems can be improved in areas of human-to-human interactions and relations. Finally, we suggest that real value and impact are generated through the (inter)action that happens around the static components of the system, and not because of them. The following chapters therefore highlight people around the EPCs, rather than the EPCs themselves, and suggest ways (and tools) for thinking towards improved EPCs and EPC Systems in a harmonised² way all across Europe.

1.4 WP5 and T5.5 infographics

With respect to the crossCert project structure, this report offers an overview of topics researched in Work Package 5 (WP5), titled *Towards people-centred EPCs*, complemented with relevant conclusions from other crossCert WPs. The chapters of this deliverable largely reflect the WP5 task structure:

- Task 5.1 – User experience of contemporary EPC Schemes
- Task 5.2 – Design and experience of EPC products and services
- Task 5.3 – Training and education of EPC Assessors
- Task 5.4 – Promotion and marketing of EPC products and services

Foundations for WP5 were established in Task 5.1, which aimed to provide the crossCert project consortium with a better understanding of existing EPC attitudes, expectations, and needs. Results from T5.1 are gathered in the Deliverable 5.1 (Bančić and Vetršek 2022) that served as an extensive resource of insights and actionable ideas for the entire WP5, many of them cornerstone for project outcomes presented in this report. Readers interested in people-centred aspects of all things EPC, or in applied interdisciplinary research in general, are invited to turn to D5.1 for insights complementary to those presented in this report, including a brief history of the EPBD, an analysis of EPC Schemes and Systems based on contrasting aspects of theory and practice, and an attempt to analyse EPCs as a social object³.

The centrepiece of this report are the four infographics presented in the chapters following the introduction, covering topics from the WP5 tasks listed above:

- 1st infographic – EPC Journey

² Each chapter offers insights and recommendations applicable across Europe which relevant stakeholders (policy makers and implementors) can transfer to their specific national contexts and tailor to their context-specific needs. T5.5 therefore does not suggest specific recommendations on how to harmonise EPC products and services at the European level. It does, however, contribute towards a harmonised understanding of the different aspects of the EPC Systems, which certainly can support, influence or prompt relevant thought processes, such as policy making, policy implementation, research planning or impact assessments, to name a few.

³ In simplified terms, *social objects* (Nevile et al. 2014; Wagner et al. 2018), or simply *things* (Antczak and Beaudry 2019; Ingold 2012), are material or immaterial objects that imply some form of a relation(ship) between the object and humans. As such, they are interpreted in socially and culturally specific ways, or differently, they are (re)presented and (re)produced in ways that carry specific meanings, much of which have little or nothing to do with the objective (measurable) properties of the object. See crossCert D5.1 (Bančić and Vetršek 2022) for a more elaborate explication of the notion, based on the case of EPCs.

- 2nd infographic – EPC Design
- 3rd infographic – EPC Assessor’s Journey
- 4th infographic – EPC Promotion and Marketing

The infographics, produced independently from other WP5 tasks but informed by their parallel research activities and outcomes, were designed with the aim to (1) support better understanding of existing EPC Systems, (2) highlight the role of people (different stakeholder profiles) involved in the systems, (3) guide structured analysis and assessment of the existing systems, and perhaps most importantly, (4) to define opportunities for improvement of existing EPC products and services, or even development of completely new ones. One of our key design goals was that anyone reading these infographics, be it an expert in the EPBD, EPCs, or a layperson with very little technical knowledge, will be able to gain a better understanding of the EPC System and how different EPC products and services come together and form part of the system. Another goal, this time targeting specifically members comprising the EPC Service Support Network at both national and international (European) levels, was to guide the readers’ thought process towards identifying potential improvements of the existing EPC systems, particularly in a form of enhanced people-centred design. Finally, our intent was that graphic materials produced in T5.5 and presented in this report can also be used as (1) promotional materials by those that raise public awareness about the importance of EPCs, (2) didactic materials by those who teach EPC-related topics, or (3) workshop materials by those who plan workshops on EPC related topics.

EPC infographic key

Readers will note that crossCert infographics use several elements and symbols to indicate important layers of presented information. Some of them are straightforward while other deserve additional explanation and contextualisation, not only for a better understanding of the infographics but also for a better appreciation of the design:

EPC Profiles

Icons for EPC Profiles indicate that EPC Profiles refer to the generalised characteristics and roles of people involved in the EPC Systems. The icons simultaneously stress the characteristic attributes associated with their role of these key stakeholder groups (a suitcase, a book, a cog, a house) as well as the fact that profile descriptions, despite stressing the roles and responsibilities associated with stakeholder groups, it is not some abstract concepts or job descriptions who we are talking about but real people interacting in spontaneous everyday life settings.

Profiles’ involvement level

KEY – The level of involvement and responsibility is high.

INDIRECT – The level of involvement and responsibility is medium.

CONTEXTUAL – The level of involvement and responsibility is low.

Key challenge

Key issues associated with individual steps, complemented with a guiding question aimed at provoking solution-oriented thinking.

Key milestones or signposts

Milestones or signposts indicating key moments on a journey, marking the step that leads into a new phase.

1.5 Chapter summaries

The introduction highlights some foundational considerations that enable us to better understand and appreciate the need for a people-centred analysis of all things EPC, stressing the contrast with otherwise predominant expert-centric (technical) and policy-centric ways of thinking about the EPCs. While the previously mentioned D5.1 was primarily analytical, challenging the widespread implication that EPCs are inherently good and useful, a viewpoint uncritically assumed by most policy-focused writing associated with the EPBD and the EPCs, the D5.5 is primarily suggestive, challenging the disproportionate attention dedicated to quality of EPCs and the excellence of the calculation methodology.

The second chapter presents the EPC Journey infographic, mapping the process of creation of the EPCs. It offers a wide-angle perspective on people-centred aspects associated with the EPC assessment service. While the EPC is the unifying element of all the steps presented in the infographic, the primary purpose is to highlight the people involved in the process of producing and using the EPCs, and to show that the value of EPCs is created exactly through interactions of the people around it.

The third chapter presents the aspect of EPC Design. The infographic guides the reader's thought through stages of Design thinking, tailored to the specific case of designing EPC products and services. The main message of the infographic is that policy makers and implementers need to consider other parts of the EPC System as seriously as they consider the EPCs (the final product), and that the development process needs to involve a number of relevant stakeholders as collaborators in the design process as much as reasonably possible.

The fourth chapter describes the career path of EPC Assessors with a stress on the training and education elements. Similar to the EPC Journey, the EPC Assessor's Journey infographic maps the steps that people pursuing a career of an EPC assessor need to take in order to become certified. It highlights the unique role EPC Assessors play in the context of EPC Systems and suggest a couple of critical points for optimisation of their journey, which would have a positive impact on the functioning of the EPC System.

The fifth chapter presents the aspect of promotion and marketing of all things EPC. The infographic highlights the importance of people-centred campaigns, starting with the analysis of target groups, crafting messages, and identifying communication channels before moving on to creating tailored campaign plans, and executing these plans. Key recommendations highlight the importance of addressing broader motivations, utilising trusted networks, and delivering clear, engaging information.

In addition to the presentation of the infographics, the reader will note that this report offers a summary of recommendations, examples of good practice, and further reading specific to the topic of the chapter. Most of these are simple summaries equipped with references that read the reader to the original source for more information, many including a direct web-link to the source. The same goes with details regarding elements of ethnographic research conducted in the context of WP5 (interviews, focus groups, field visits), the reader will find more details on these with corresponding visual materials in the corresponding reports for Tasks 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4. The final noteworthy element of this report is the D5.5 booklet (see Annex), joining the four EPC infographics in a user-friendly printable (A3) format.

2 The EPC Journey

2.1 What is the EPC Journey?

The crossCert EPC Journey describes the creation of an EPC. It is a map of steps involved in obtaining and utilising an EPC, keeping the EPC as the focal point of the mapped process, yet highlighting the key stakeholders involved at each step. It enables us to focus on the people and their interactions around the EPCs, highlighting the relevance of practical and performative aspects of EPC assessment and certification.

The EPC Assessment Service (steps 3-6) is at the core of the journey, outlining dynamics between the service provider (the EPC Assessor) and the customer, contextualised with key steps before and after the service takes place, which provide the basis for the EPC products and services to create value for everyone involved, and have a meaningful impact on the world.

Readers should note that the infographic is a generalisation and does not refer to any specific national EPC System. As implied in the purpose of crossCert project, which is to compare not only the EPCs but to understand the differences in the system and suggest ways to harmonise them across Europe, the EPC Journey in each country looks slightly different. Some countries spend more time on certain steps than others and there can be significant difference in how the individual steps are realised (who are the responsible actors, what support services the countries have in place, etc.). The crossCert EPC Journey was intentionally developed to function as a tool to think about the existing EPC Systems in a structured manner, to function as a reference point for comparison of the different national schemes, and to search for possible improvements.

CROSSCERT EPC JOURNEY

2.2 Key steps in the EPC Journey

2.2.1 Raise awareness

The fundamental first step on the EPC Journey is to equip people with the basic knowledge they need to understand how EPCs can have a meaningful impact on their everyday professional and personal lives. This understanding will help them to engage proactively in the following steps of the journey.

1 RAISE AWARENESS

RAISE AWARENESS

The fundamental first step on the EPC Journey is to equip people with the basic knowledge they need to understand how EPCs can have a meaningful impact on their everyday professional and personal lives. This understanding will help them to engage proactively in the following steps of the journey.

KEY CHALLENGE: Lack of strategies and resources targeting awareness raising.

How to demonstrate that EPCs are more than just an administrative requirement, but a meaningful part of life in contemporary European societies?

- EPC Service Support Network
- EPC Expert Users, EPC Assessors
- EPC General Users

2.2.2 Engage

In cases where EPCs are decisively beneficial or factually required by law, key stakeholders need to have a good understanding of their responsibilities towards the EPC system that call for their action, as well as the case-specific privileges and benefits that are expected to motivate their engagement.

2 ENGAGE

ENGAGE

In cases where EPCs are decisively beneficial or factually required by law, key stakeholders need to have a good understanding of their responsibilities towards the EPC system that call for their action, as well as the case-specific privileges and benefits that are expected to motivate their engagement.

KEY CHALLENGE: Poorly communicated stakeholder responsibilities and associated benefits.

How to communicate individualized case-specific motives and obligations regarding ordering or using EPCs, and how to integrate EPC assessment with activities and processes that are meaningful in people's lives?

- EPC Service Support Network
- EPC Expert Users, EPC Assessors
- EPC General Users

2.2.3 Arrange the Assessment

Clients' first contact with the EPC service provider, aimed at arranging practical details of the assessment, is the first step in the EPC Assessment Service. Despite its organisational focus, this step is pivotal in creating value for the client, demonstrating professionalism and building solid ground for delivering good value throughout the following steps.

3

ARRANGE THE ASSESSMENT

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Clients' first contact with the EPC service provider, aimed at arranging practical details of the assessment, is the first step in the EPC Assessment Service. Despite its organizational focus, this step is pivotal in creating value for the client, demonstrating professionalism and building solid ground for delivering good value throughout the following steps.

KEY CHALLENGE: Poor qualities and practices in EPC customer service.

How to enhance the value proposition for the customer? How to improve the arrangement process, making it more effective, simpler, effortless and value-driven?

EPC Assessors, EPC General Users

EPC Service Support Network, EPC Expert Users

2.2.4 Gather Data & Information

Following the arrangements, the service provider needs to collect data and information required for calculating and issuing the EPC. This includes details on the building's construction, occupancy, and energy consumption. A site visit by a qualified EPC assessor is the most common and most reliable method in the established EPC assessment practice.

4

GATHER DATA & INFORMATION

GATHER DATA & INFORMATION

Following the arrangements, the service provider needs to collect data and information required for calculating and issuing the EPC. This includes details on the building's construction, occupancy, and energy consumption. A site visit by a qualified EPC assessor is the most common and most reliable method in the established EPC assessment practice.

KEY CHALLENGE: Limited interaction between customers and EPC assessors.

How to improve the interaction between the EPC assessor and the client during the on-site visit? How to motivate EPC assessors to deliver better service, and clients to be more engaged?

EPC Assessors, EPC General Users

EPC Service Support Network, EPC Expert Users

2.2.5 Process Data & Information

Once the assessor gathers all the necessary data & information it has to be processed according to the established national protocol. This mainly involves office work, to calculate the EPC indicators and to complete administrative actions required to issue the EPC as an official document.

5

PROCESS DATA & INFORMATION

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Once the assessor gathers all the necessary data & information it has to be processed according to the established national protocol. This mainly involves office work, to calculate the EPC indicators and to complete administrative actions required to issue the EPC as an official document.

KEY CHALLENGE: Optimization of work required by EPC assessors.

How to optimize the calculation method and user interface of the calculation software? How to optimize the administrative process of issuing the EPCs as official documents?

- EPC Assessors
- EPC Service Support Network
- EPC Expert Users, EPC General Users

2.2.6 Issue & Deliver EPCs

Delivering the EPC to the client is the closing phase of the EPC Assessment Service. The final product should be interpreted, contextualised and presented in a way that meets or surpasses the client's expectations. In most cases, the service provider also needs to deposit or register the EPC with the appointed authority or institution.

6

ISSUE & DELIVER EPCs

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KEY CHALLENGE: Lack of interest and engagement on one or both sides of the service.

How to motivate both the service provider and the recipient to dedicate time and attention at the moment of EPC delivery?

- EPC Assessors, EPC General Users
- EPC Service Support Network, EPC Expert Users

2.2.7 Use EPCs

The usability of EPC products and services should be considered a key element of the EPC concept, as this ultimately translates into value and meaning for the institutions and the people who should benefit from it. EPCs should therefore not only *inform* about buildings' energy performance but also *support* and *enable* meaningful actions and transactions.

7

USE EPCs

USE EPCs

The usability of EPC products and services should be considered a key element of the EPC concept, as this ultimately translates into value and meaning for the institutions and the people who should benefit from it. EPCs should therefore not only inform about buildings' energy performance but also support and enable meaningful actions and transactions.

KEY CHALLENGE: Poor integration of EPCs with actions and processes associated with buildings.

How to enhance the integration of EPCs with goal-oriented processes, transactions or other activities associated with the built environment which are already well-established and meaningful to people?

EPC Expert Users, EPC General Users

EPC Service Support Network, EPC Assessors

2.2.8 Repeat

EPCs of today have a temporary value, as they are a static description of the building's energy performance at the time of their issuing. With time, the factors that define buildings' performance change, as do the policies and regulations that define the current EPC systems. A periodic update of EPCs is therefore necessary to ensure their relevance.

8

REPEAT

REPEAT

EPCs of today have a temporary value, as they are a static description of the building's energy performance at the time of their issuing. With time, the factors that define buildings' performance change, as do the policies and regulations that define the current EPC systems. A periodic update of EPCs is therefore necessary to ensure their relevance.

KEY CHALLENGE: Lack of awareness and materialized benefits associated with periodic updates of EPCs.

How to increase awareness of the need to update existing EPCs periodically, and demonstrate how the benefits of updates materialize in practice?

EPC Assessors, EPC General Users

EPC Service Support Network, EPC Expert Users

2.3 Recommendations

Key recommendations related to the EPC Journey based on results of work done in WP5 are:

- Improve the design of the existing EPC products and services.
- Develop or enhance interactive features in the design of EPC products and services.
- Ensure EPC Systems and associated policy areas are people-centred, high-quality, and socially just.
- Target specific user-profiles and tailor EPC products and services to match their specific interests and purpose of use.
- Consider differences in accessibility for different social groups.
- Develop new EPC business models to scale up the rate of certification.
(all from Bančič and Vetršek 2022)

Readers will also find a long list of recommendations for improvements of the EPC Systems in D5.1, based mostly on U-CERT and IDEAL EPBD project outcomes (see Bančič and Vetršek 2022: 74-83).

2.4 Further reading

Readers interested in understanding and developing the EPC Systems should read about conceptual frameworks from Social Sciences and Humanities, such as the **dramaturgical analysis framework** developed by a sociologist Erving Goffman (see Bančič and Vetršek 2022: 63-67) or the **theory of social practice** as refined by a sociologist Elisabeth Shove, economist Mika Pantzar, and geographer Matt Watson (see Bančič and Vetršek 2022: 67-70). In D5.1, we do not try to explain these theories as much as attempt at applying them on the case of the EPC assessment and certification to indicate how they can be used in pursuits of future improvement and development of the national EPC Systems.

crossCert *D2.3 Recent EPC initiatives across Europe 3rd version* (Taxeri 2023) includes a list of EU initiatives dealing specifically with the “human factor” (ibid: 21-23). An interesting account of an EPC-related customer journey analysis was provided by the UK’s Department of Energy & Climate Change (2013) and, on a related note, a more general analysis of customer journeys regarding household energy investments by Nieboer and Straub (2018).

3 The EPC Design

3.1 What is the EPC Design?

In crossCert, by referring to **EPC Design** we refer to design of both EPC product *and* services. In other words, we refer both to the process of creating and structuring the visual and informational elements of EPCs (the product), as well as developing effective people-centred procedures for assessing and certifying buildings' energy performance (the service). The notion therefore encompasses:

- **The graphic elements** such as visual representations of energy efficiency ratings (often displayed as color-coded bars or scales), icons, and layout designs that make the information easily understandable and visually appealing.
- **The content elements** such as data or information on a building's energy consumption, potential energy savings, recommendations for improvements, and specific metrics such as CO₂ emissions. An example and an important aspect associated with the design of EPC content is organisation of displayed content with regard to its relevance and complexity for a specific use case.
- **The service design elements** such as the methodology and protocols used for evaluating a building's energy performance. It includes the tools and standards employed by certified EPC Assessors to communicate with their clients, conduct on-site inspections of the buildings, analyse data, issue EPCs, and possibly support their clients in actually using the EPC after they have received it.

Good EPC Design should aim towards delivering real value to the customers. This implies clear, concise, and comprehensive ways of engaging with key stakeholder profiles – for example, effectively informing property owners about the potential to renovate their property and optimise their energy use. Furthermore, good EPC Design also encompasses accuracy, reliability, and consistency of certification services or other auxiliary services that enhance the value of EPCs and the EPC System. Neither products nor services should be considered as completely standalone entities, although they often function as such. We believe good EPC services are what gives validity to EPCs as final products, as well as has potential to vastly enhance their usability in the eyes of the customer receiving or interpreting an EPC.

The second crossCert infographic introduces the notion of **Design thinking**. This is an iterative problem-solving approach that emphasises empathy, collaboration, and experimentation. Throughout this process, it's essential to maintain a people-centred mindset, involving stakeholders at every stage to ensure that the outcomes truly meet the needs of the people they are intended to serve. When applied to the specific case of **EPC Products and Services**, our design thinking approach needs to ensure that EPCs contribute towards the core purpose of the EPCs and the EPC Systems across Europe, which is to promote energy efficiency, sustainability, and transparency in the built environment. Besides supporting thinking for improvement of existing EPC Products and Services, the purpose of this infographic is therefore to guide the reader towards innovating new products and services that will fit into this category. This is indicated in Step 6 of the infographic, which suggests innovation of services that support EPC application and use, as well as a digital EPC as a new product. In terms of impact and meaning, EPC Products and Services are considered especially valuable when they support decision making for building renovations.

Design Thinking for Impactful & Meaningful Design of EPC Products & Services

Design thinking is a people-centred iterative problem-solving approach that emphasizes empathy, collaboration, and experimentation. Throughout this process, it's essential to maintain a people-centred mindset, involving stakeholders at every stage to ensure that the outcomes truly meet the needs of the people they are intended to serve, as well as to ensure they contribute towards the core purpose of the Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) and EPC systems across Europe - to promote energy efficiency, sustainability, and transparency in the built environment and to support decision making for building renovations.

6. IMPLEMENT
Develop a plan for the full-scale implementation of new solutions or a change management plan for the already existing EPC products or services. Collaborate with key stakeholders to integrate the solutions into the existing processes and systems. Consider scalability, cost-effectiveness, and long-term maintenance requirements. Monitor and evaluate the implementation to ensure it meets the defined goals and objectives.

5. TEST
Conduct usability testing and gather feedback on the prototypes. Assess the performance, user experience, and effectiveness of the proposed energy-efficient solutions. Identify any issues or areas for improvement and refine the prototypes accordingly. Keep the purpose of the EPC system firmly in mind throughout; this process and observe if tested solutions lead towards desired results.

4. PROTOTYPE
Develop prototypes for the most promising ideas shaped in the previous step. For physical or technology-based solutions, create physical or digital prototypes that illustrate functionality. For behavioural interventions, consider creating simulations or interactive experiences to test user engagement; for instance with the EPC of the building.

3. IDEATE
Generate a wide range of creative ideas for addressing the problems and opportunities defined in the previous step. Conduct brainstorming sessions, engage team members from a variety of backgrounds, and involve the people for whom you are developing. Explore both technological and behavioural solutions, products, and services, and prioritize them based on feasibility, impact, and alignment with user needs.

2. DEFINE
Define clear problem statements by synthesizing the information gathered during the empathy phase. Identify typical profiles and specify typical problems and goals they associate with energy efficiency in buildings. Also, define how these relate to your own objectives associated with EPC products and services, and search for synergies.

1. EMPATHIZE
Understand the needs and challenges of the people you wish to address - building occupants, owners, and others interested in the topic of energy in buildings. Engage with a wide range of stakeholders to gather insights into energy consumption patterns, user behaviours, and pain points; these people meaningfully associate with the topic.

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 855203. Views and opinions expressed are only those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official position of the Commission, nor does it guarantee the accuracy of the information presented therein.

3.2 Key steps in the People-Centred EPC Design process

3.2.1 Empathize

Understand the needs and challenges of the people you wish to address – building occupants, owners, and others interested in the topic of energy in buildings. Engage with a wide range of stakeholders to gather insights into energy consumption patterns, user behaviours, and pain points these people meaningfully associate with the topic.

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3.2.4 Prototype

4 PROTOTYPE

Develop prototypes for the most promising ideas shaped in the previous step. For physical or technology-based solutions, create physical or digital prototypes that illustrate functionality. For behavioural interventions, consider creating simulations or interactive experiences to test user engagement.

3.2.5 Test

5 TEST

Conduct usability testing and gather feedback on the prototypes. Assess the performance, user experience, and effectiveness of the proposed energy-efficient solutions. Identify any issues or areas for improvement and refine the prototypes accordingly. Keep the purpose of the EPC system firmly in mind throughout this process and observe if tested solutions lead towards desired results.

3.2.6 Implement

6 IMPLEMENT

Develop a plan for the full-scale implementation of new solutions, or a change management plan for the already existing EPC products or services. Collaborate with key stakeholders to integrate the solutions into the existing processes and systems. Consider scalability, cost-effectiveness, and long-term maintenance requirements. Monitor and evaluate the implementation to ensure it meets the defined goals and objectives.

3.3 Recommendations

Key recommendations related to EPC Design based on results of work done in WP5 are:

- Rather than radically changing the established EPCs, future developments of EPCs should build on existing formats and designs.
- New indicators may need to be added to existing EPC content to increase value of the EPCs for various user groups.
- Significant attention needs to be devoted to striking the right balance between detail (complexity of information) and generalisations (simplicity of information) to avoid information fatigue on the one hand and satisfying needs of diverse user groups on the other.
- For optimal design of EPC products and services, to ensure they effectively cater to the needs of different user groups, it is crucial to consider the diverse perspectives and expectations of users.
- Based on the crossCert T5.2 workshop results, a generalised preference for an EPCs design turned out to be a multi-page document that makes use of multiple presentational forms of data (graphical, tabular, text), but uses online (digital) resources to expand on this beyond the traditional hard-copy of the EPC.
- Based on the crossCert T5.2 workshop results, participants saw value in having improvement recommendations that are more specific to a property rather than generalised.
- To inform the development of future EPCs, we need a more comprehensive understanding of users' attitudes and expectations, particularly from respondents in other European countries. Further studies of diversity of EPC users should therefore be undertaken, considering geographical, and cultural, professional factors as well as other significant aspects relevant to the specific location and participant group.
(all from Jenkins et al. 2024)

In addition to the above, our research indicates that policy implementers also need to:

- Diversify the scope of design efforts – pursue development of innovative EPC products and services, such as digital EPCs, support services for applicative use of EPCs, etc.
- Involve designers in the process of EPC Design or organise an EPC design contest.
- Build a brand out of national EPCs, which might include designing EPC merchandise and building associations between EPCs and the notion of responsible ownership and good management.

3.4 Examples & good practices

Readers interested in innovations in EPC design should read a series of blog posts⁴ issued by the X-tendo project, describing testing of innovative features and their replication potential from their case studies in nine European countries (Austria, Italy, Estonia, Denmark, Poland, Romania, Greece, Scotland and Portugal). The EPBD.wise project highlighted 'owner oriented' or 'multi-purpose' design of EPCs from Portugal and Denmark (Carvalho et al. 2024: 23) as examples of good practices.

3.5 Further reading

Readers interested in our research on design and experience of EPC products and services should read the crossCert Deliverable 5.2 – Survey and workshop results of EPC end-users (Jenkins et al. 2024). The report presents the results of two separate user engagements – a survey on user attitudes towards EPC inputs

⁴ See: <https://x-tendo.eu/blog/> [Last accessed: 11. 7. 2024]

and outputs (ibid: 6-11) and an online workshop titled 'Designing the perfect EPC – What works for you?' (ibid: 12-17). The insights and outcomes produced in the task are contextualised with graphs and charts as well as graphic materials used in the workshops. In addition, readers will find an extensive list of recommendations for improvement of EPC Design gathered in crossCert Deliverable 5.5 (Bančič and Vetršek 2022: 74-83), mainly summarised from results of projects U-CERT and IDEAL EPBD. A list of design recommendations associated with the idea of developing an EPC translating tool can be found in D4.3 (Hrbud 2024, chapter 2.2.1), while D4.2 includes notes on adapting EPCs to user and investor needs (Cadórniga Pedrosa and Fernández Fernández 2024).

A number of similar and complementary design implications and suggestions can also be found in X-tendo project's guidance note for the next-generation EPC scheme (Zuhaib et al. 2020), deliverables of U-CERT project (Bančič et al. 2020; Bančič et al. 2021) and a position paper by The European Consumer Organisation (BEUC 2021).

4 The EPC Assessors' Journey

4.1 What is the EPC Assessors' Journey?

EPC Assessors play a pivotal role in delivering the EPC certification service, and are arguably the people who (should) carry the largest responsibility with regards to how people experience the service, how they will establish their perceptions and opinions about EPCs, and what kind of effect the service will have with regard to the expected added value(s) of EPCs. As such, they are the cornerstone of the national EPC Systems and widely recognised as key actors in realising the purpose of EPCs.

The crossCert EPC Assessor's Journey maps key steps by which EPC Assessors progress in their career and contribute towards keeping the system in function. Each step of the journey represents a reflection point to understand better the role of EPC Assessors, and search for potential improvements of the existing system in the future. Despite the specific focus on EPC Assessors, the purpose of this infographic is to support future advancement of the EPC System for the benefit of all EPC Profiles involved in its functioning.

Readers should note that the infographic is a generalisation and does not refer to any specific national training schemes. As Simeonov (2024) clearly shows in his analysis of training and education services in the crossCert project countries (Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Denmark, Greece, Malta, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and the UK), the EPC Assessors' Journey in each country looks slightly different. Some countries spend more time on certain steps than others, or even bypass some of the steps. The crossCert EPC Assessor's Journey was intentionally developed to function as a tool to think about the existing training schemes in a structured manner, to function as a reference point for comparison of the different national schemes, and to search for possible improvements.

EPC ASSESSOR'S JOURNEY

4.2 Key steps on the EPC Assessor's Journey

4.2.1 Inform and motivate

Access to adequate information is the key prerequisite to spark an interest in prospective EPC Assessors to begin their training journey. Potential candidates need to understand the general purpose & goals of the EPC System, and to grow motivated, they need to understand how EPCs are related to their personal professional goals and aspirations.

1

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! KEY CHALLENGE: Recognition of the role of EPCs.
How to onboard committed professionals that will bring the purpose of the EPC System to life?

- EPC Service Support Network
- EPC Assessors
- EPC General Users, EPC Expert Users

4.2.2 Engage

As the first step, interested candidates need to apply with the establishments that offer training courses or certification. In most EU countries, candidates must meet specific educational background requirements (in engineering, architecture, or similar technical expertise) or prove specific professional experience in a relevant field of work.

2

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! KEY CHALLENGE: Differences in EPC training frameworks.
How to harmonize the training frameworks across Europe for enhanced effectiveness of EPC Systems?

- EPC Service Support Network, EPC Assessors
- EPC General Users, EPC Expert Users

4.2.3 Train and build competence

Following successful application, the candidates receive a combination of theoretical courses and materials, practical training, and learning support from the training provider. The institutional frameworks across Europe vary substantially both in terms of content (structure, length, and balance of theory and practice) and organisation (the degree to which they are regulated, institutionalised, or open to the market).

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! KEY CHALLENGE: Unharmonized training content.
How to design the training to optimize the learning experience and maximize the benefit for training participants?

- EPC Service Support Network, EPC Assessors
- EPC General Users, EPC Expert Users

4.2.4 Certify

In most European countries, candidates need to pass an official post-training examination if they wish to obtain the status of a certified EPC Assessor. Typically, the exam consists of a theoretical and practical part, the latter being focused on mastering the process of collecting and processing of data for production of the EPCs.

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! KEY CHALLENGE: Different competences of the EPC Assessors
How to harmonize the learning objectives across Europe to ensure optimal qualification standards for EPC Assessors?

- EPC Assessors, EPC Service Support Network
- EPC General Users, EPC Expert Users

4.2.5 Practice EPC assessment

Certified EPC Assessors are the primary ambassadors of the EPC System, raising public awareness about the relevance of the EPC System and offering their services to all segments of the system. This implies communication with the clients, gathering and processing of the necessary data and information, energy modelling, identifying suitable energy savings measures, and ultimately issuing and delivery of the EPCs.

5

PRACTICE EPC ASSESSMENT

PRACTICE EPC ASSESSMENT

Certified EPC Assessors are the primary ambassadors of the EPC System, raising public awareness about the relevance of the EPC System and offering their services to all segments of the system. This implies communication with the clients, gathering and processing of the necessary data and information, energy modelling, identifying suitable energy savings measures, and ultimately issuing and delivery of the EPCs.

! KEY CHALLENGE: Inconsistent quality of EPC assessments.

How to motivate EPC Assessors to deliver top quality service to their customers and the system?

EPC Assessors, EPC Expert Users, EPC General Users

EPC Service Support Network

4.2.6 Perform quality checks

Continuous quality control and efforts for improvement are essential for maintaining high quality standards and public trust in the EPC System. In this regard, all EPC Assessors should periodically undergo performance checks. Poor performance should be adequately addressed while outstanding performance should be recognised and rewarded.

6

PERFORM QUALITY CHECKS

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Continuous quality control and efforts for improvement are essential for maintaining high quality standards and public trust in the EPC System. In this regard, all EPC Assessors should periodically undergo performance checks. Poor performance should be adequately addressed while outstanding performance should be recognised and rewarded.

! KEY CHALLENGE: Insufficient quality control.

How to streamline quality control and reward top-performing EPC Assessors?

EPC Service Support Network

EPC Assessors

EPC General Users, EPC Expert Users

4.2.7 Contribute to the EPC community

Experienced assessors should share their knowledge and experience with peers, promote best practices, and contribute to the overall development and improvement of the EPC System. The focus is on fostering professional growth of community members through mutual support and cooperation for the advancement of the field of expertise.

7

CONTRIBUTE TO THE EPC COMMUNITY

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Experienced assessors should share their knowledge and experience with peers, promote best practices, and contribute to the overall development and improvement of the EPC System. The focus is on fostering professional growth of community members through mutual support and cooperation for the advancement of the field of expertise.

! KEY CHALLENGE: Lack of positive identification with the role of an EPC Assessor.

How to motivate EPC Assessors to actively contribute towards the community of EPC professionals?

EPC Service Support Network

EPC Assessors

EPC General Users, EPC Expert Users

4.2.8 Upskill and grow professionally

Energy performance in buildings is a rapidly evolving field of expertise. Periodic refresher courses, advanced qualification trainings, and other forms of upskilling are available in several European countries. Although not universally obligatory, practising EPC Assessors are widely expected to participate and pursue continuous professional growth.

8

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! KEY CHALLENGE: Adequate response to the growing ambition in building renovation.

How to motivate EPC Assessors to actively seek professional advancement for the benefit of the EPC System?

EPC Service Support Network, EPC Assessors

EPC General Users, EPC Expert Users

4.3 Recommendations

In crossCert Deliverable 5.3, we define a number of recommendations for improvement of current assessor's training across Europe. Some of the most relevant include:

- Introduce mandatory training for EPC assessors in all European countries.
- Introduce mandatory periodic complementary training or upskilling in all European countries.
- Tailor the training to the needs and expectations of training participants, including the balance between the frequency and intensity of training, flexibility, and the associated costs of the training.
- Avoid content or training practices that participants find unnecessary or repetitive.
- Enhance the practical part of the training and optimise the theoretical content.
- Introduce different levels of qualification of EPC assessors according to the complexity of buildings they are trained to assess (simple vs. complex).

The recommendations summarised above are further elaborated in D5.3, accompanied by several national-level recommendation (ibid: 25-28) and recommendations from other Next Generation EPC projects (QualDeEPC, TIMEPAC, EUBSuperHub and others).

4.4 Examples & good practices

Readers interested in good practices in EPC systems and certification, including those related to training and education of EPC Assessors, should read the QualDeEPC project's *D2.2 Report on EPC best practices* (Kostova et al. 2020). They list both recommendations for 'enhanced and converging EPC scheme' (ibid: 45-54) as well as existing best practices (ibid:35-45) from an impressive number of European countries, including Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxemburg, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovak Republic, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, The Netherlands and UK-England. The EPBD.wise project highlights Sweden's approach to EPC 'Expert Training' as a shining example (see Carvalho et al. 2024: 22) as well as good practices such as quality control from both Portugal and Ireland (ibid.: 23).

4.5 Further reading

Readers interested in the topic of training and certification of EPC Assessors should read our full *D5.3 Report on training and education services for certified EPC issuers* (Simeonov 2024). It includes a comparative analysis of specialised training and education programmes in crossCert countries (ibid: 6-20) and identifies gaps (ibid: 21-24) based on which the recommendations for improvement of existing national training schemes, which we have summarised above, are elaborated (ibid: 24-31). The report also describes the qualitative methods used to produce the deliverable, including interviews and consultations with key national EPC stakeholders, and includes ethnographic evidence (photos and notes) of these interactions for each of the countries (ibid: 34-80).

Readers will also find a dedicated section with recommendations for improvements of training and education of EPC Assessors in D5.1, based mostly on U-CERT and IDEAL EPBD project outcomes (see Bančič and Vetršek 2022: 82-83).

5 EPC Promotion & Marketing

5.1 What is the EPC Promotion & Marketing?

Public opinion matters when it comes to creating effective policy, and EPBD is no exception to that. In crossCert *Deliverable 5.4 – Report on Promotion and Marketing of EPC Products and Services*, Turfin (2024) notes that marketing and promotional campaigns are crucial to motivate homeowners to undertake energy renovations. People are often satisfied with their buildings and reluctant to start a complex renovation process due to unclear benefits, she adds, and goes on to argue that the typical campaigning watchwords about financial benefits, assuming that property owners make rational decisions based on cost savings, are not enough. What we need, she points out, is more people-centred promotion and communication campaigns that resonate with people's daily lives and broader motivations.

The fourth crossCert infographic, **EPC Promotion and Marketing**, emphasises the people-centred strategy. Our approach consists of three stages. In the ideation phase, we analyse target groups, craft key messages, and identify effective channels. The creation phase assembles these elements into actionable campaign plans tailored to our audience. Finally, the implementation phase puts these plans into real-life action, supporting informed building renovation decisions and fostering sustainable futures across Europe. The core message, however, is not as much *how* to craft the campaigns, but simply that -by default- promotion and marketing strategies should be considered an integral part of the policy implementation process. Only thus will we be able to optimise the influence of EPCs on energy efficiency, sustainability, and transparency in the built environment, and counter the negative pushback that policy makers and implementers are experiencing in many countries around Europe.

EPC PROMOTION & MARKETING

To optimize the influence of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) on energy efficiency, sustainability, and transparency in the built environment, promotion and marketing strategies should be considered an integral part of the policy implementation process.

The crossCert approach to EPC Promotion and Marketing emphasizes a people-centred strategy that consists of three stages. In the **ideation phase**, we analyse target groups, craft key messages, and identify effective channels. The **creation phase** assembles these elements into actionable campaign plans tailored to our audience. Finally, the **implementation phase** puts these plans into real-life action, supporting informed building renovation decisions and fostering sustainable futures across Europe.

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5.2 Key steps in planning an effective campaign

5.2.1 The target groups

The target group of our communication campaign is never, and should never be, considered as a homogeneous group. Property owners, for example, do not all share the same behavioural characteristics and everyday-life circumstances, such as the sociodemographic background, environmental concerns, dwellings characteristics, or perception on energy production and use. Similarly, they do not share the same opportunities, such as more or less favourable fiscal and regulatory policies, or access to capital.

It is therefore essential to consider a few questions to identify this group. Turfin (2024) suggest the concept of lifestyle typology developed by the Sinus Institute, and recognised in Germany as the basic model for societal analysis in the social sciences, can help us to better identify our target group and define messages that appeal to them, using the communication channels they use (ibid: 23). This concept divides society into 10 different lifestyles (conservative, liberal-intellectual, high achiever, movers and shakers, adaptive pragmatics, social-ecological, new middle class, traditional, precarious, escapist) depending on their belonging to a social milieu but also according to their beliefs and values (orientation).

5.2.2 The message

Defining "the message" in EPC promotion and marketing campaigns is crucial. If we take energy efficiency in built environment as a case, messages should bundle energy-efficient measures with broader home improvements, targeting underlying motivations like life events and gradual renovations. Highlight benefits such as funding access, comfort, and property value. Emotional appeals, evoking positive feelings, are more effective than rational ones. The message should be engaging and leave conclusions open for customer response. Strategic approach that considers specific conditions of domestic life, triggers that prompt people to act, and the specific benefits implied in doing a specific action are more likely to resonate emotionally with the homeowners and encourage energy-efficient renovations. Campaigns should provide reliable, visually appealing information that is clear, simple, and personally relevant. The latter is especially important, as each of the crafted messages should be matched to a specific target profile to provoke the desired emotion and/or (re)action.

5.2.3 The communication channels

Effective EPC promotion and marketing campaigns must utilise diverse communication channels to reach all potential renovators. Mass media channels, including the internet, flyers, mail, radio, TV, and press articles, are crucial for disseminating information widely. However, trusted person-to-person channels, leveraging the influence of people’s professional and social networks, such as peers, co-workers, family and friends, deliver the message with a higher level of impact as they often imply more credibility and attractiveness. Direct personal contact in general drives the message further. Door-to-door energy advice and neighbourhood approaches, also have a significant margin of impact.

Specialised information sources, such as energy agencies or consumer organisations, as well as sources which are widely regarded as trustworthy and reliable, such as government homepages, are another important reference point for influencing public opinion and building confidence and trust in the EPC Systems.

5.2.4 Create tailored campaigns

Planning effective tailored campaigns is critical for successful EPC promotion and marketing. The process involves defining clear objectives that build on (1) understanding of the target audience, (2) crafting engaging messages tailored to the target audience, and (3) defining the channel that suits best to the job.

It also includes allocating resources efficiently to maximise impact. A detailed timeline with key milestones and continuous performance measurement through analytics is essential. Consideration of all of these steps ensures that campaigns resonate with the audience, address their needs and concerns, and ultimately encourage energy-efficient renovations.

5.2.5 Campaign

Effective implementation of EPC promotion and marketing campaigns hinges on thorough execution and strategic alignment with broader energy renovation goals. As noted earlier, campaigns should present reliable, clear, and accessible information about EPCs using various communication channels, including the internet, TV, radio, and print media. Utilising visually appealing and relatable content, such as inspiring stories and practical advice, helps to engage homeowners. Trusted individuals and organisations should convey the messages to enhance credibility. Additionally, personal advice formats like door-to-door consultations and neighbourhood initiatives are valuable for raising awareness and motivating action. Coordination among stakeholders, including banks, energy advisers, and real estate

agents, is essential to reinforce the campaign's impact. Most significantly, however, best campaigns are run with a level of enthusiasm and engagement. Campaigning “because we have to” or “because it’s the law” will unlikely be as effective and impactful as campaigning because we actually want to.

5.3 Recommendations

Key recommendations related to EPC Promotion and Marketing based on results of work done in WP5 are:

- Create campaigns that resonate with the property owners and their daily life using storytelling and various formats to reach a diverse audience. More specifically, align the campaigns with the life cycles of the inhabitants (arrival of a child, retirement, heritage of real estate, etc.) and/or trigger points leading to renovation (roof, kitchen, and/or bathroom renovation, facade renovation, house extension).
 - Highlighting benefits that go beyond technical and financial details of building renovation, such as indoor comfort, health and safety.
 - Build communication campaigns for promotion of EPBD policies, EPCs, and energy renovation of buildings on strong foundations, using appealing, reliable and widely recognised information. Trust is an essential consideration in this regard, so developing campaigns that engage close communities (friends, neighbours and family) with the participation of a professional should be considered a promising approach.
 - Leverage various media and formats—such as websites, leaflets, and free information lines—to reach a broad audience of property owners.
 - Improve the perception of EPBD policies and EPCs among key professional profiles, such as EPC assessors, real estate agents, bankers and others who influence general public perceptions of value and usefulness of EPCs through their own everyday professional practice.
 - Provide tailored training to each of the professional profiles mentioned above, not only to improve their acceptance of EPCs but to show them how they can enhance the value of their service, as well as of the EPCs, by using EPCs in their professional practice.
 - Prior to implementing legislative changes, develop strategies to mitigate the financial impact of legislative changes associated with the EPBD on citizens and to address the fears caused by these legislative changes.
 - Prior to implementing legislative changes, develop counter-strategies to address the likely negative reactions, and to limit the spread of false information.
- (all from Turfin 2024)

5.4 Examples & good practices

Readers interested in good (and bad) practices in EPC promotion and marketing should read about how banks in Denmark use EPCs for marketing of their own services and financial products, how video campaigns are used in Spain and the UK to contextualise use of EPCs in campaigns for efficient energy use, how fairs and promotion campaigns are used by some Austrian energy suppliers to build positive public awareness about EPCs, and many more such examples from crossCert countries, collected in our

report on promotion and marketing of EPC products and services (see Chapter 2 in Trufin 2024: 37-54) and contextualised with short descriptions and graphical illustrations.

Trufin highlights the German consumer advice centre Verbraucherzentrale⁵ as a good example of how energy advice should be communicated through multiple formats, including telephone, online, and in-person consultations. On a related note, the EPBD.wise project highlighted Scotland's HES OSS as a comprehensive resource for homeowners seeking to improve energy performance (Carvalho et al. 2024: 23).

5.5 Further reading

Readers interested in EPC promotion and marketing should read our report on promotion and marketing of EPC products and services (Trufin 2024). It includes a comprehensive summary of the theory of promotion and marketing (ibid: 10-21), guidelines and suggestions for crafting an impactful campaign (ibid: 21-30), and an extensive analysis of the recent public debate about the Building Energy Act in Germany, as framed by some of the biggest media outlets in Germany (ibid: 55-68). The report also includes a list of policy recommendations (ibid: 79) derived from the analysis presented in the report and a concluding argument why promotion and marketing of EPCs should be considered an integral part of the policy implementation process (ibid: 79-80).

Readers will also find a dedicated section with recommendations for improvements of promotion and marketing of EPCs in D5.1, based mostly on U-CERT and IDEAL EPBD project outcomes (see Bančič and Vetršek 2022: 81-82).

⁵ Available online: <https://www.verbraucherzentrale.de/ueber-uns> [Last visited: 24. 7. 2024]

6 Conclusions

This report underscores the critical role of people around the Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs), especially when thinking about how to improve existing EPCs and EPC Systems to make them more people-centred and to enhance the EPBD policy impacts. The infographics presented in the report, which are the most relevant independent outcome of Task T5.5, explore the EPC journey, design, assessor's role, and promotional strategies. They serve as a tool for EPC experts and policy makers at all levels for defining opportunities for improvement of existing EPC Systems from the people-centred point of view and can be used by a variety of different profiles and use scenarios, such as awareness raising, educational activities and promotion.

The EPC Journey infographic maps several key steps of EPC service, including raising awareness, engaging stakeholders, arranging assessments, gathering data, issuing EPCs, and encouraging their use. Harmonising standards for high quality people-centred EPC services across different national systems is recommended to ensure consistency and effectiveness. A holistic approach aims to streamline the process for both property owners and professionals, making it more impactful and ultimately valuable for everyone involved.

People-centred design of EPC products and services involves empathising with users, defining their needs, ideating solutions, prototyping, testing, and implementing the final design. The goal is not only to provide clear, concise, and comprehensive information on the EPC (final product), but to complement this with quality services that enhances the value and usability of EPCs. Ensuring accuracy, reliability, and consistency in certification services is crucial for building trust and encouraging widespread adoption.

The role of EPC assessors is vital, encompassing stages from informing and motivating prospective assessors to continuous professional development. Assessors (should) undergo rigorous training and certification processes, followed by practical assessments and quality checks. Supporting assessors through ongoing education and community involvement ensures high standards and fosters a knowledgeable and skilled workforce.

Effective promotion and marketing strategies are essential for increasing EPC awareness and acceptance. Tailored messages, appropriate communication channels, and people-centred campaigns can address broader motivations and deliver clear information. Building a strong national EPC brand and involving designers in the process can further enhance the system's appeal and effectiveness.

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8 Annex

ANNEX 1: People-Centred EPC Products and Services (Printable booklet)

PEOPLE-CENTRED EPC PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

PEOPLE-CENTRED EPC PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

Welcome to People-Centred EPC Products & Services, an infographic booklet that defines Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) as social objects – things that exist within networks of socio-cultural relations and influence the dynamics of our everyday life. The booklet presents various segments of the EPC System, highlighting areas with significant potential for enhanced people-centred design. Developed in collaboration with a professional designer, these infographics serve as a tool for analysing and assessing the current state of EPC Systems across Europe.

Whether you're an EPC professional or someone seeking to understand the complexities of EPC Systems, you'll find these infographics invaluable. They break down the EPC System into logical building blocks, offering insights for improvement. Additionally, these visuals can be used to promote public awareness, serve as educational materials, or facilitate specialized topical workshops. Our aim is to provide a comprehensive, user-friendly resource that illuminates the people-centric nature of EPCs, fostering a better understanding and more effective implementation of EPC-associated policies. For more information, visit the crossCert website (www.crosscert.eu) or read crossCert Deliverable 5.5 - Towards people-centred EPCs: Guidelines and recommendations for development of people centred EPC products and services.

PEOPLE-CENTRED EPC PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

24 July 2024

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Why This infographic Matters

The crossCert EPC Journey describes the creation of an **Energy Performance Certificate (EPC)**, an official document used to rate the energy performance of buildings. It is a map of steps involved in obtaining and utilizing an EPC, keeping the EPC as the main 'protagonist' of the mapped process, yet highlighting the key stakeholders involved at each step. The **EPC Assessment Service** is at the core of the journey, outlining dynamics between the service provider and the customer, contextualized with key steps before and after the service takes place, which provide the basis for the EPC products and services to create value for everyone involved, and have a meaningful impact on the world.

EPC System

The EPC system is a functional network of stakeholders and institutions that enable, co-create and otherwise support the existence and functioning of the national EPC schemes. Besides people who drive the system, it includes the **EPC Scheme** – a conceptual and legislative framework that includes protocols and methods that define the national rules and standards regarding the issuing of EPCs – and other non-animate means they use in their efforts to keep the system working.

EPC Profiles

EPC Service Support Network refers to profiles that develop the conceptual framework for implementation of the national EPC schemes, as well as stakeholders that enable and/or implement (enforce or exercise) the official conceptual framework.

EPC Expert Users are people assumed to possess considerable knowledge in the area of buildings and the built environment, which also implies a capacity to interpret EPCs as advanced users, and possibly use EPCs as part of their professional practice.

EPC Assessors are people trained and certified to do EPC assessments. In essence, they are part of the EPC service support network yet play a pivotal role in translating EPC theory into practice, connecting the EPC system with the public.

EPC General Users are people assumed to possess a lesser extent of relevant EPC-related knowledge yet are expected to interpret and use EPCs meaningfully in pursuit of their specific goals related to buildings.

Involvement level

- KEY** The level of involvement and responsibility is high.
- INDIRECT** The level of involvement and responsibility medium.
- CONTEXTUAL** The level of involvement and responsibility is low.

Legend

- KEY CHALLENGE** Key issues associated with individual steps, complemented with a guiding question aimed at provoking solution-oriented thinking.
- Milestones**

Design Thinking for Impactful & Meaningful Design of EPC Products & Services

Design thinking is a people-centred iterative problem-solving approach that emphasizes empathy, collaboration, and experimentation. Throughout this process, it's essential to maintain a people-centred mindset, involving stakeholders at every stage to ensure that the outcomes truly meet the needs of the people they are intended to serve, as well as to ensure they contribute towards the core purpose of the Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) and EPC systems across Europe – to promote energy efficiency, sustainability, and transparency in the built environment and to support decision making for building renovations.

6. IMPLEMENT

Develop a plan for the full-scale implementation of new solutions or a change management plan for the already existing EPC products or services. Collaborate with key stakeholders to integrate the solutions into the existing processes and systems. Consider scalability, cost-effectiveness, and long-term maintenance requirements. Monitor and evaluate the implementation to ensure it meets the defined goals and objectives.

5. TEST

Conduct usability testing and gather feedback on the prototypes. Assess the performance, user experience, and effectiveness of the proposed energy-efficient solutions. Identify any issues or areas for improvement and refine the prototypes accordingly. Keep the purpose of the EPC system firmly in mind throughout this process and observe if tested solutions lead towards desired results.

4. PROTOTYPE

Develop prototypes for the most promising ideas shaped in the previous step. For physical or technology-based solutions, create physical or digital prototypes that illustrate functionality. For behavioural interventions, consider creating simulations or interactive experiences to test user engagement, for instance with the EPC or the building.

3. IDEATE

Generate a wide range of creative ideas for addressing the problems and opportunities defined in the previous step. Conduct brainstorming sessions, engage team members from a variety of backgrounds, and involve the people for whom you are developing. Explore both technological and behavioural solutions, products, and services, and prioritize them based on feasibility, impact, and alignment with user needs.

2. DEFINE

Define clear problem statements by synthesizing the information gathered during the empathy phase. Identify typical profiles and specify typical problems and goals they associate with energy efficiency in buildings. Also, define how these relate to your own objectives associated with EPC products and services, and search for synergies.

1. EMPATHIZE

Understand the needs and challenges of the people you wish to address – building occupants, owners, and others interested in the topic of energy in buildings. Engage with a wide range of stakeholders to gather insights into energy consumption patterns, user behaviours, and pain points these people meaningfully associate with the topic.

△ Before - The introduction

○ During - The training

□ After - The service

1

INFORM AND MOTIVATE

Access to adequate information is the key prerequisite to spark an interest in prospective EPC Assessors to begin their training journey. Potential candidates need to understand the general purpose & goals of the EPC System, and to grow motivated, they need to understand how EPCs are related to their personal professional goals and aspirations.

KEY CHALLENGE: Recognition of the role of EPCs.

How to onboard committed professionals that will bring the purpose of the EPC System to life?

Want to become an EPC Assessor

2

ENGAGE

As the first step, interested candidates need to apply with the establishments that offer training courses or certification. In most EU countries, candidates must meet specific educational background requirements (in engineering, architecture, or similar technical expertise) or prove specific professional experience in a relevant field of work.

KEY CHALLENGE: Differences in EPC training frameworks.

How to harmonize the training frameworks across Europe for enhanced effectiveness of EPC Systems?

Attend training

3

TRAIN AND BUILD COMPETENCE

Following successful application, the candidates receive a combination of theoretical courses and materials, practical training, and learning support from the training provider. The institutional frameworks across Europe vary substantially both in terms of content (structure, length, and balance of theory and practice) and organisation (the degree to which they are regulated, institutionalized, or open to the market).

KEY CHALLENGE: Unharmonized training content.

How to design the training to optimize the learning experience and maximize the benefit for training participants?

Attend training

4

CERTIFY

In most European countries, candidates need to pass an official post-training examination if they wish to obtain the status of a certified EPC Assessor. Typically, the exam consists of a theoretical and practical part, the latter being focused on mastering the process of collecting and processing of data for production of the EPCs.

KEY CHALLENGE: Different competences of the EPC Assessors

How to harmonize the learning objectives across Europe to ensure optimal qualification standards for EPC Assessors?

Study hard!

5

PRACTICE EPC ASSESSMENT

Certified EPC Assessors are the primary ambassadors of the EPC System, raising public awareness about the relevance of the EPC System and offering their services to all segments of the system. This implies communication with the clients, gathering and processing of the necessary data and information, energy modelling, identifying suitable energy savings measures, and ultimately issuing and delivery of the EPCs.

KEY CHALLENGE: Inconsistent quality of EPC assessments.

How to motivate EPC Assessors to deliver top quality service to their customers and the system?

Do the first EPC assessment

6

PERFORM QUALITY CHECKS

Continuous quality control and efforts for improvement are essential for maintaining high quality standards and public trust in the EPC System. In this regard, all EPC Assessors should periodically undergo performance checks. Poor performance should be adequately addressed while outstanding performance should be recognised and rewarded.

KEY CHALLENGE: Insufficient quality control.

How to streamline quality control and reward top-performing EPC Assessors?

Strive for excellence

7

CONTRIBUTE TO THE EPC COMMUNITY

Experienced assessors should share their knowledge and experience with peers, promote best practices, and contribute to the overall development and improvement of the EPC System. The focus is on fostering professional growth of community members through mutual support and cooperation for the advancement of the field of expertise.

KEY CHALLENGE: Lack of positive identification with the role of an EPC Assessor.

How to motivate EPC Assessors to actively contribute towards the community of EPC professionals?

Gain experience

8

UPSKILL AND GROW PROFESSIONALLY

Energy performance in buildings is a rapidly evolving field of expertise. Periodic refresher courses, advanced qualification trainings, and other forms of upskilling are available in several European countries. Although not universally obligatory, practicing EPC Assessors are widely expected to participate and pursue continuous professional growth.

KEY CHALLENGE: Adequate response to the growing ambition in building renovation.

How to motivate EPC Assessors to actively seek professional advancement for the benefit of the EPC System?

Advocate sustainable future for Europe

Why This infographic Matters

EPC Assessors are the cornerstone of the **EPC System** and are widely recognized as key actors in realizing the purpose of EPCs. The crossCert **EPC Assessor's Journey** maps key steps by which they progress in their career and contribute towards keeping the system in function. Each step of the journey represents a reflection point to understand better the role of EPC Assessors, and search for potential improvements of the existing system in the future. Despite the specific focus on EPC Assessors, the purpose of this infographic is to support future advancement of the EPC System for the benefit of all **EPC Profiles** involved in its functioning.

EPC System

The EPC system is a functional network of stakeholders and institutions that enable, co-create and otherwise support the existence and functioning of the national EPC schemes. Besides people who drive the system, it includes the **EPC Scheme** – a conceptual and legislative framework that includes protocols and methods that define the national rules and standards regarding the issuing of EPCs – and other non-animate means they use in their efforts to keep the system working.

EPC Profiles

EPC Service Support Network refers to profiles that develop the conceptual framework for implementation of the national EPC schemes, as well as stakeholders that enable and/or implement (enforce or exercise) the official conceptual framework.

EPC Expert Users are people assumed to possess considerable knowledge in the area of buildings and the built environment, which also implies a capacity to interpret EPCs as advanced users, and possibly use EPCs as part of their professional practice.

EPC Assessors are people trained and certified to do EPC assessments. In essence, they are part of the EPC service support network yet play a pivotal role in translating EPC theory into practice, connecting the EPC system with the public.

EPC General Users are people assumed to possess a lesser extent of relevant EPC-related knowledge yet are expected to interpret and use EPCs meaningfully in pursuit of their specific goals related to buildings.

Involvement level

- KEY**
The level of involvement and responsibility is high.
- INDIRECT**
The level of involvement and responsibility medium.
- CONTEXTUAL**
The level of involvement and responsibility is low.

Legend

- KEY CHALLENGE**
Key issues associated with individual steps, complemented with a guiding question aimed at provoking solution-oriented thinking.
- Key signpost**

To optimize the influence of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) on energy efficiency, sustainability, and transparency in the built environment, promotion and marketing strategies should be considered an integral part of the policy implementation process. The crossCert approach to EPC Promotion and Marketing emphasizes a people-centred strategy that consists of three stages.

In the **ideation phase**, we analyse target groups, craft key messages, and identify effective channels. The **creation phase** assembles these elements into actionable campaign plans tailored to our audience. Finally, the **implementation phase** puts these plans into real-life action, supporting informed building renovation decisions and fostering sustainable futures across Europe.

1. IDEATION PHASE

KNOW WHO YOU WISH TO COMMUNICATE TO
Target group / Persona

Behavioral

- Dwelling characteristic**
Surface, age, individual house, energy performance, localisation
- Sociodemographic characteristics**
Age, income, presence of children
- Environmental concerns**
Waste separation, public transportation, ...
- Energy context perception**
Risk aversion

Structural

- Fiscal and regulatory policies**
- Access to capital**

KNOW WHAT IS YOUR MESSAGE
Promotion messages

- Condition of Domestic life**
- Triggers**
- Benefits of renovation measures**

KNOW YOUR CHANNELS

Trust persons

- Social networks**
- Professional networks**

Trust information

- Government homepages**
- Energy agencies**
- Consumer organisations**

2. CREATION PHASE

Develop tailored Campaigns

3. IMPLEMENTATION PHASE

Communicate and support

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